

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D1.4 Engagement strategy & Qualitative mapping of relevant stakeholders related to the education field at the local, national, and international level

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1. Executive Summary

The Engagement strategy and Qualitative mapping of relevant stakeholders related to the education field at local, national and international level is a document that will serve as a base to maximize the strategic involvement of all types of stakeholders. This document is divided into two main sections:

- 1) description of the engagement plan for the upcoming actions to maximize the involvement of strategic stakeholders of different types.
- 2) initial database of educational stakeholders in each partner country that could potentially benefit from the involvement in the project and contribute to its development. The mapping process is in its initial stage and will be updated for the rest of the project.

The ongoing commitment to updating and refining the stakeholder database emphasises the dynamic nature of the education sector and LET'S CARE adaptability to it. Through the strategies defined in this document we aim to create a strong network of stakeholders, leveraging their strengths and expertise to enrich the project's vision and contribute to the promotion of Safe Education at various levels.

2. Introduction

2.1. What is the Stakeholders Network

LET'S CARE Network of Stakeholders is a European active environment of participation constituted by members encompassing representatives of all the relevant stakeholders to contribute to the critical process of feedback loops on the project's activities and results. It is a real and virtual space in which the principles of the Safe Education approach are promoted and supported through the involvement of scientific community, students, families, teachers, school boards, policymakers, NGOs. The Network creates a European-wide link between professionals and organizations who share common understanding of the importance of preventing exclusion, underachievement, disengagement, and school dropout through the creation of a safe educational environment for all learners.

The LET'S CARE Network is envisioned as a dynamic and structured space for engagement at a European scale, involving a minimum of 190 entities. This diverse group will include individuals from various key sectors related to the project's aims: the scientific community, educators, school administrators, policymakers, non-governmental organizations, students, and family members. Representatives will be involved at local, national, and international levels, ensuring a wide-reaching impact. By bringing together such a diverse group of stakeholders, the LET'S CARE Network aims to create a collaborative and inclusive environment where all voices are heard and valued. This comprehensive approach is expected to significantly contribute to the advancement and sustainability of Safe Education initiatives across Europe.

The LET'S CARE Consortium, and especially the "field work partners", will work to both strengthening and broadening the network, positioning it as the primary framework to facilitate ongoing involvement of various stakeholders and to encourage collaboration across diverse sectors. This network is set to play a crucial role in the vital process of evaluating the activities and outcomes of the project, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation based on stakeholder input and experiences. This process of open exchange with the members of the Network is inspired by a co-creation approach that characterizes LET'S CARE.

One of the most important tools that will be used to ensure this co-creational exchange between the Consortium and the stakeholders is the LET'S CARE Hub. The LET'S CARE Hub is the space, the container of the process, the tool that allows the meeting among ideas, activities, inputs, and direct participation. It will serve as a central platform where different stakeholders can come together to exchange their unique viewpoints, insights, and stories related to Safe Education, enriching the dialogue, and contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the issues. From the point of view of the co-creation approach, the Network is meant to capture and integrate these diverse narratives: the academic insights from the scientific community, practical wisdom from educators

and school boards, strategic input from policymakers, grassroots perspectives from NGOs, or the personal experiences of students and families.

The LET'S CARE Network will also be the crucial to inform and motivate the stakeholders in be part of the Participatory Action Research. This research methodology requires a meaningful involvement of the participants, and the structure of the Network will provide a starting point to organize the different steps of the research and to reach different target groups. This bottom-up process of creating not only research ideas but also the active participation of stakeholders at all levels is a slow process that all partners will consolidate through the elements described below. The results of the Participatory Action Research will be visible from the quality and quantity of the interventions and the direct and indirect participation in the discussions. The Participatory aspect of the PAR approach is based on 3 elements: spaces of co-creation, training to co-creation, activities of co-creation. The information events bring about motivating inputs with the aim of creating the active participation of stakeholders. These inputs can be set up through specific training moments attended by the stakeholders. These moments can be followed by targeted training and discussion sessions on the project's founding concepts that will allow participants to bring their potential contributions and ideas for school improvement into play.

2.2. Role of the Stakeholders Network members

In the LET'S CARE network, stakeholders can voluntarily choose from a variety of roles, levels of engagement and of contribution, (see below for the more detailed plan) according to their expertise, interest or time availability to be part of the transformative actions. This dynamic flexibility to determine at each time their level of involvement will facilitate an active participation by allowing members to decide their own level of contribution and workload. The distinction between different degrees of involvement within the network facilitates their contribution and engagement in accordance with current models of capacity-building that allow power-sharing between stakeholders and researchers in terms of decision-making and co-creation (Shier 2001. Lundi 2007). With this framework the network ensures a diverse and dynamic involvement, catering to the varied capacities and contributions of its members.

1. Recipients of information: At the most basic level, stakeholders can choose to be recipients of information and participants in the LET'S CARE Hub communities. In this role, they are kept informed about the project's developments, goals, and activities. This role is crucial for those who wish to stay updated and potentially share this information within their own networks, albeit without active involvement in the project's activities.

2. Contributors to dissemination: A step further involves stakeholders as multipliers of the results, contributing to the dissemination of the project's concepts and principles, centered around fostering a Safe Education environment. This role involves actively spreading awareness and information about

the LET'S CARE project within their communities and networks. They can also become first promoters of valorization activities within in the framework of the project.

3. Active participants in co-creation and PAR: Stakeholders can also choose to be more actively involved in the co-creation of knowledge¹. This role is ideal for those who wish to have a hands-on impact on the project's direction and outcomes and involves engaging in the project's research activities destined to theory building, design of data collection and intervention tools, analysis, testing and uptake. These stakeholders can also be actors of knowledge cross-fertilization among the different sectors of the network.

4. Advocates for policy and action: In the most active role from the social point of view, stakeholders can serve as advocates, supporting and promoting policy actions that align with the network's goals. This role entails actively pushing for changes, mobilizing resources, and forming alliances to support the cause of Safe Education at various levels.

To become members of the LET'S CARE Network, the stakeholders will sign an agreement which present them the different roles they can play in the Network, their rights and the data protection procedures. The agreement can be found in the Annex 1.

3. Analysis of the Stakeholders

3.1. Type of stakeholders

The network will be composed of stakeholders representing different fields and target groups in order to correspond to the various needs the project is addressing. The variability of points of view and contributions will improve the project proposals, bringing unique perspectives and expertise, and supporting the co-creative process. By engaging these stakeholders in various roles and activities, the LET'S CARE network ensures a comprehensive, collaborative, and multi-dimensional approach to promoting Safe Education.

The main type stakeholders involved will be:

- **Education Scientific Community:** This group includes European universities and research centers in education/pedagogy, developers, and other related projects. Their involvement can be in research collaborations, providing scientific insights, developing educational tools, and contributing to the network's evidence-based approach. They can also play a role in

¹ See D1.2. PAR training manual and infographics on PAR activities during project

evaluating and validating the effectiveness of the network's initiatives through rigorous academic methodologies.

- **Teachers' Community:** Comprising schoolteachers, educators, and other school staff such as counselors and non-teaching personnel, this group can provide valuable feedback on the practical aspects of educational initiatives, ensuring they are feasible and effective in real-world settings. Teachers can also actively participate in the LET'S CARE Hub sharing good practices and Safe Teaching strategies. Teachers' associations and networks can facilitate wider dissemination and adoption of successful practices.
- **Schools:** Scholar institutions, boards, non-formal educational environments (after-school and sport centres, associations, second-chance schools) can be involved in integrating the network's initiatives into their curricula and programs. They can provide a practical perspective on how policies and ideas translate in real educational settings, sharing their experience in the LET'S CARE Hub.
- **Policymakers and Authorities:** This group includes public institutions responsible for assessing and approving national and regional education plans, as well as creators and administrators of policy measures aimed at improving educational outcomes. Their involvement is crucial in aligning the network's goals with national and regional policies, facilitating the adoption of successful practices on a broader scale, and ensuring sustainability.
- **Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and Advocacy Organizations:** These entities can be involved by supporting grassroots initiatives, promoting the network's goals to wider audiences, and providing support to marginalized communities. They can also help in mobilizing resources, creating partnerships for the network, and disseminating the project's results.
- **Students' Family Environment:** Involving parents, legal guardians, and other family members, can participate in community engagement activities, provide feedback on how educational changes impact their children, and support learning outside the formal school environment. Their involvement ensures that the network's initiatives are family-friendly and consider the home's role in education.
- **Learners' Representatives:** Especially those from challenging contexts, these representatives can provide firsthand insights into the unique needs and challenges faced by learners in different environments. Their involvement ensures that the network's initiatives are inclusive and effectively address the diverse needs of all learners.

The direct involvement of the stakeholders in the construction and representation of all aspects of the network's actions, may directly or indirectly involve their entire institution/organization. The participants can join the network representing themselves or the whole institution / organization and they can opt for this option when subscribing. Even when network members participate as individuals, the reference to their institutions of origin is important because it constitutes the theoretical background that characterizes their involvement and enriches the network through their direct experience, the activities that are already being carried out in their institutions and the functional and organizational models which they implement or know. Their participation as representatives of an institution/organization is also a two-way channel for reflection, within the spaces for dialogue provided by the project, on possible aspects of future exploitation and sustainability. This valorisation of the institutions represented by the network members is also of great importance because it qualifies the project's interventions and demonstrates the concreteness of the relationship between experience and the possibilities of change to create a real Safe School.

3.2. Geographical level of impact

Involving stakeholders in the education sector at all geographical levels is crucial for fostering a collaborative, inclusive and high-quality Network. In line with the co-creation and Participatory Action Research approach, by embracing diverse perspectives, expertise, and resources, stakeholders can collectively contribute to shaping LET'S CARE educational policy recommendations, initiatives, and reforms. This collaborative approach ensures that the LET'S CARE network will remain responsive and effective in meeting the needs of learners and society. As explained in D1.2, co-creation with PAR methodology is meant to foster a meaningful level of involvement in which participants have the opportunity to express their views within a safe environment. The aim is to address horizontally and vertically the aspects that characterise these problems with moments of dialogue and reflection that start from local needs to reach the political and social dimension at European level. This leads stakeholders from reasoning about local needs to a global vision of the project's objectives and enables them to understand the LET'S CARE potential and the value of their contribution for the impact that can be achieved at a political level.

At the **local level**, stakeholders have a deep understanding of the unique challenges and needs of their specific community. Their involvement ensures that educational policies and initiatives align with the local context, leading to more effective and relevant outcomes. The impact at the local level is based on needs and discrepancies highlighted during the project. The debate then spreads to regional and national level, bringing the issues to a broader scale and involving politics increasingly. Involving stakeholders at the **regional level**, including educational institutions and policymakers, can facilitate collaboration and knowledge-sharing to address common challenges and work towards

shared goals. By pooling resources and expertise, regions can implement innovative approaches, exchange best practices, and enhance the overall quality of education. Involving stakeholders at this level promotes regional cooperation, leading to a more cohesive and interconnected education system.

Involving stakeholders at the **national level** is crucial for ensuring comprehensive educational reforms and policy development. National stakeholders, such as government officials, education experts and civil society organizations, offer diverse perspectives and valuable insights. Their involvement helps in setting strategic priorities and establishing standards.

The LET'S CARE stakeholder network becomes a space for constructive growth but also a moment of common reflection on the needs at European level to address difficulties, to fight school drop-out and low academic achievement, consolidating the project's impact. European stakeholders, including policymakers, educators, and researchers, can collaborate across borders to address common challenges and promote educational excellence. Involvement in European initiatives allows for the exchange of ideas, best practices and experiences, fostering innovation and enhancing the quality of education throughout the continent. Moreover, involving stakeholders at the **European level** strengthens European identity and cooperation, contributing to a more cohesive and inclusive education system.

4. Engagement strategy

The setting up of an engagement strategy of relevant stakeholders related to education plays a crucial role in the success of any project aimed at improving the educational policy proposal. In line with this, the partners of the LET'S CARE project have devised a comprehensive communication and engagement plan to establish and develop a robust network of stakeholders.

The primary objective of the engagement strategy is to foster collaboration and collective action among various stakeholders, such as policymakers, educators, parents, students and community leaders, to address the challenges faced by the education sector. By engaging these key players, the project aims to create a platform for knowledge sharing, ideas exchange and capacity building (through the LET'S CARE Hub). This strategy will be revised and updated when necessary.

Although the partners have already started to approach the stakeholders through communication activities, the proper creation of the LET'S CARE Network will start from M12, supported by the launch of the LET'S CARE Hub.

4.1. Levels of engagement

To develop an engagement strategy for stakeholders, it is possible to follow the same levels identified in LET'S CARE Communication and Dissemination plan (D6.2). We have delineated four distinct levels

of stakeholder engagement which correspond to increasingly comprehensive levels of information, communication and participation. Ideally, each representative of the stakeholders should go through each level becoming more and more involved in the project activities and co-creation process.

Awareness: Initial introduction and acquaintance about the project.

Information: provide further details via the LET'S CARE Hub, participatory events and online newsletter/ blog.

Know-how: Dissemination of specific contents related to the project, mostly through materials available on the Hub platform and specific training events.

Engagement: Active involvement in the project's initiatives in 3 main ways:

- a) Regular updates on project progress via collaborative platforms, such as discussion chats, both at the international and national levels.
- b) Active attendance and contribution at scheduled events.
- c) Collaboration as external specialists to provide feedback and contributions to the conceptual and methodological aspects (WP1-3) and/or to the final results and the subsequent recommendations (WP3-6).

Figure 1 – Progressive structure of the stakeholders engagement, reflecting the number of potential addressees

4.2. Topics addressed at the different engagement levels

For each level of engagement, we plan to convey different messages and to address different topics to stimulate the interest and the participation of the stakeholders.

Awareness

This level is the first step to make the stakeholders know about the existence of Let's Care and to raise awareness about its goals to foster synergies. The main topics that are addressed by the activities implemented at this level to engage the stakeholders are:

- Inclusive education to remove the barriers faced by students in vulnerable conditions.
- The interaction of gender equality and education, specifically how gender dynamics may impact safe-teaching competencies.
- The significance of child attachment, teacher-student attachment relationships, and the role of school climate in fostering academic engagement, achievement and success.
- The socio-economic benefits of Safe Education for students and their broader environment, emphasizing aspects such as enhanced well-being, strengthened social ties within educational communities, improved future opportunities for children, and an enriched sense of community belonging.
- The benefits of being an active participant within the LET'S CARE Network and Community.

Information

The second level offers the stakeholders a deeper understanding of the project and its methodologies. Predominantly disseminated through the project's website, as well as via conferences, seminars, and other project-related activities, this phase addresses the following themes to engage stakeholders more effectively:

- Presentation of the project's core objectives, outcomes, and instruments.
- Insights into the data collection processes, employed methodologies, and panels of indicators or databases.
- Presentation of the scientific findings of the project, including the holistic model for Safe Education.
- A comprehensive description of LET'S CARE Tools, alongside results from pilot testing.
- Examination of LET'S CARE's tangible outcomes and its socio-economic implications.
- European events tailored for educators and teaching professionals.
- LET'S CARE events and advocacy initiatives.

Know-how

In this level the involvement of the stakeholders is more direct and they are invited to support the project's actions. They can access the project results and provide feedback. The main topics that are addressed in this phase to engage the stakeholders are:

- Identifying the needs of schools and students according to a "whole organisation approach" – this encompasses the schools, child and youth centers, and second chance school settings.
- Safe Education model and its implementation in schools.
- Legal, ethical considerations, potential obstacles, and prerequisites for the successful execution of LET'S CARE.
- Participative techniques.
- Delving into self and peer observation techniques, complemented by relevant tools.
- Guidelines on Safe Teaching Practices: strategies for successful introduction, enhancement, and replication.
- Introduction to Safe Education evaluation tools, including the utilization of e-profiles or the school label.

Engagement

In this final level, stakeholders transition from mere participants to change agents within their respective fields. They are actively involved in proposals, assimilating and employing strategies, concepts, or methodologies that have been cultivated. To inspire and motivate stakeholders during this decisive phase, attention is centered on the following themes:

- Promote inclusion in the educational environment.
- Collaborate to develop a caring school environment.
- Participation in data collection, mutual collaborations, and tools' validation processes.
- Increasing collaboration between researchers and creating synergy with complementary projects.
- Align the project to both EU and national requisites or needs.
- Promote the endorsement of policy recommendations upon the project's completion.

4.3. Communication channels

The stakeholders' engagement strategy will use the same communication channels identified in the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

The main channels that will be used to involve the stakeholders during the first 2 phases of **Awareness** and **Information** will be:

- **Social Media Campaigns:** By leveraging the reach and influence of social media platforms, we aim to connect with broader audiences. This involves sharing timely project updates, circulating important research results, and initiating discussions on the role of a caring perspective in educational inclusion and success.
- **Press Releases and Media Outreach:** A dual-fold approach involving the creation of compelling press releases and fostering bonds with media outlets. The goal is to enhance the visibility of the project's message and achievement, reaching not just the general audience but also educational and policy communities.
- **Newsletters and Email Campaigns:** we will produce newsletters and email communications to the subscribers, providing an overview of the project's trajectories, research findings, upcoming events, and possible cooperation. This channel of communication aims to sustain engagement with stakeholders, keeping them informed about the project.
- **Information Meetings and Seminars:** these meetings and seminars will involve teachers, school administrators, policymakers and community leaders, to discuss the Safe Education model and its implementation. These events will provide a platform for sharing insights, best practices, and innovative approaches related to the Safe Education model and its implementation.
- **Public Speaking Engagements:** Being present in relevant seminars, panel discussions and public events as speakers or contributors, we aim to disseminate the project's values, research findings, and policy recommendations to a multifaceted audience. Such engagements will open doors for networking, alliances and cross-cooperation.

For the **Know-how** and **Engagement** phase the partners will preferably organize:

- **In-person and Online Meetings at Various Levels:** These sessions, ranging from local to national scales, are designed to disseminate the project results, foster dialogues with stakeholders, ensuring they are continually updated and allowing to collect their feedback.
- **Co-hosted events:** partners will assist local stakeholders in organizing public events that focus on the primary topics of Safe Education.

- **Transnational meetings of the network:** partners will facilitate the meetings of the representatives from different countries in order to improve the European connection and cooperation in the educational field.

4.4. Main messages conveyed

The success of the engagement strategy relies on a proper use of the messages conveyed to the target groups. The partners will adapt the contents and the structure of the messages to the actual needs and culture of their countries, but the general overview of the most important elements can be provided.

MAIN TOPICS AREA OF INTEREST	MESSAGE TO BE CONVEYED
Students and their security in relation with the family, teachers, schools and community	<p>The social well-being of a child plays a pivotal role in their educational progress and commitment to attending school.</p> <p>When children have secure relationships, they show improved social curiosity, experience fewer conflicts with peers, and display a greater willingness to learn.</p> <p>Establishing strong relationships with families, teachers, schools and communities fosters a sense of emotional security and self-control, both of which are crucial for academic success and active participation.</p>
Teachers and their relations to students and their families	<p>The relationships between teachers and students are fundamental indicators of academic achievement, psychological well-being, and motivation to succeed in school.</p> <p>These relationships have a significant impact on students' progress and engagement at various stages of their educational journey, both in direct and indirect ways.</p> <p>Attachment theory provides a valuable framework for comprehending the importance of these relationships in children's development, and ongoing research in this field presents fresh prospects for examining and intervening in teacher-child relationships.</p>
School organisation and community	<p>A positive school climate plays a crucial role in enhancing both academic outcomes and the personal growth and well-</p>

	<p>being of students, while also reducing student absenteeism. It offers numerous advantages, exerting a strong impact on students' motivation to learn and reducing violence. Additionally, it acts as a safeguard for learning, counteracting the detrimental effects of socioeconomic factors on academic achievement.</p>
<p>Policy and society</p>	<p>To gain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges associated with early school leaving and academic struggles, we must transcend the narrow scope of the school context and take into account social exclusion as a significant contributing factor.</p> <p>There has been a notable change in the perspective regarding students facing difficulties in school, considering “educational exclusion” as part of the causes of the school failure. This broader concept acknowledges the influence of external factors such as personal circumstances, family situations, and economic conditions.</p>

5. Communication procedures

To effectively communicate with and motivate stakeholders to become active members of the LET'S CARE Network, a comprehensive and dynamic communication strategy will be employed. This strategy is designed to engage stakeholders in a meaningful and consistent manner, fostering a sense of community and collaboration. Partners will support the implementation of this strategy in their countries by adapting the contents and the actions to the local realities and stakeholders’ needs.

Initially, partners within the network will undertake a systematic approach to gather contact information from interested stakeholders. This process will involve compiling a **database**, which will serve as the base of all communications. The database will not only store contact information but will also categorize stakeholders based on their areas of interest and expertise. This categorization will enable targeted and relevant communication.

A **mailing list** will be established to provide stakeholders with regular updates, news, and invitations to participate in various activities. To keep stakeholders continuously engaged and informed, regular updates will be circulated. These updates will include success stories, progress reports, upcoming events, and opportunities for participation. The content will be crafted to be engaging and informative, highlighting the impact of the network and the valuable role of each stakeholder.

Stakeholders will be invited to join the **LET'S CARE Hub** to facilitate discussion and collaboration. The Hub will act as a virtual meeting place where stakeholders can share ideas, engage in discussions, and stay informed about the network's activities and progress. Thanks to the different resources it will ensure a rich and interactive experience.

Within the LET'S CARE Hub the stakeholders can find **thematic sub-communities** that can answer to the diversity of stakeholders' interests and expertise. will be. These sub-communities have been created on Viber and allow for more focused discussions and sharing among stakeholders with similar interests or roles. This approach not only facilitates deeper engagement on specific topics but also helps in building smaller, more intimate communities within the larger network.

An integral part of the communication strategy will be a feedback mechanism. Stakeholders will be encouraged to provide feedback on the network's activities, communication effectiveness, and their overall experience. This feedback will be crucial for continuously improving communication strategies and ensuring that they meet the evolving needs of the network's stakeholders.

6. Work plan

In these initial months the partners have conducted a mapping exercise to identify the relevant stakeholders. The stakeholders have been mapped in each piloting country according to the type of target group they represent and the geographical level of impact of their activities. The partners have also analysed how these stakeholders can contribute to the project and how to involve them. This process has helped us to understand the diverse perspectives, interests and potential contributions of each stakeholder group. For each stakeholder the partners have identified the main contact person, but the data cannot be publicly shared for the protection of the personal data. Summarizing the information collected is possible to quantify the potential impact reached by this first mapping

TYPES OF TARGET GROUPS	GEOGRAPHICAL SCOPE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students: 28 organizations / institutions ● Students' families: 24 organizations / institutions ● Education scientific community: 27 organizations / institutions ● Teachers' community: 25 organizations / institutions ● Schools: 15 organizations / institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local: 33 organizations / institutions ● Regional: 33 organizations / institutions ● National: 51 organizations / institutions ● European / International: 55 organizations / institutions

- **Policy makers and authorities (local, regional, national):** 35 organizations / institutions
- **European policy makers:** 11 organizations / institutions
- **NGOs and advocacy organizations:** 40 organizations / institutions
- **Citizens, media outlet and general public:** 11 organizations / institutions

The detailed list of mapped stakeholders, broken down by country, can be found in Annex 2. At the actual moment the subscription of the stakeholders to the Network is still informal and the majority of the stakeholders involved have received information about the project. These initial contacts has supported the implementation of the PAR activities in WP3 and 12 stakeholders (mainly school directors) have been involved in the in-depth interviews. Annex 3. reports the list of the main stakeholders involved by Month 12.

While implementing the mapping exercise, some of the partners have already contacted part of the stakeholders, and informally invited them to participate to the LET'S CARE Network. The partners have communicated with the stakeholders, mostly thorough direct contacts, in informal meetings or during other communication events. Some of them have used the digital communication to address the stakeholders and provide them more information. A European and International research has been implemented to complete the framework of the network and to plan outreach activities to include in the Network other countries.

From the very beginning of the project, the partners stressed the need to create a tension and focus on the objectives of LET'S CARE and how to involve all stakeholders at different levels and stages. The Consortium decided to launch the process starting from the teachers. They have been involved through direct actions that laid the foundations for collaboration and participation. There have been organised micro-sectoral training and information sessions about practical strategies for inclusive teaching, pedagogical approaches that put the learners at the center of the educational process, well-being, cooperative learning, promote critical thinking and personal reflection in children, use of art and creativity as inclusive strategy for students with intellectual disabilities and behavioural issues. These events may have seemed disjointed, but like small pieces of a jigsaw puzzle, they created a pathway to bring teachers and stakeholders closer to an awareness of a need they had not yet explored and to understand the real message brought by LET'S CARE.

The engagement strategy presented above will be put in place by the consortium in the following 36 months of the project. This time schedule is a general indication of the main steps to be implemented,

but it has to be taken into consideration that the process of involving stakeholders will be continuous throughout the project.

Throughout these 36 months, regular communication, monitoring of activities, and adaptation based on ongoing feedback will be crucial. The success of this action plan hinges on the active and sustained

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involvement of all stakeholders, as well as the flexibility to adapt to emerging needs and opportunities.

Once the stakeholders have been identified, the project partners will employ a range of communication and engagement activities to establish connections and build relationships. This will include, as presented above, organizing workshops, seminars and conferences to facilitate dialogues and the exchange of ideas. Furthermore, LET'S CARE Hub will be used to reach a wider audience and promote meaningful exchange among the stakeholders. Through these efforts, the Consortium is committed to fostering positive change in the education sector and improving the lives of students, educators, and communities as a whole.

All partners will work beyond the project duration towards the growth and enrichment of this network, which will become a key source of innovative research, practice testing, synergy creation and collaboration and clustering activities that will constantly feed European decision-making processes. It is expected that the network will grow up to 300 groups of stakeholders identified and engaged, reaching at least 35 organizations among public authorities, 40 NGOs/Civil Society, 5 supranational teachers' associations, 5 supranational parents' associations, 200 schools, 6 academic institutions, in Europe.

Annex 1 – Template for the informed consent for the Let's Care Network of Stakeholders

Responsible LET'S CARE partner:

[Add name and contact details of organisation and the specific person in charge for LET'S CARE].

Dear *****,

You are receiving this information because we would like to invite you to take part in the

LET'S CARE project aims to comprehensively understand and improve the caring dimension of educational inclusion and school success.

In particular, we want to invite you to the LET'S CARE Network of Stakeholders. This Network is envisioned as a dynamic and structured space for engagement at a European scale, aims to create a collaborative and inclusive environment where all voices about Safe Education are heard and valued. This network is set to play a crucial role in the vital process of generating and maintaining the project's feedback loops and for evaluating the activities and outcomes of the project, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation based on stakeholder input and experiences.

With the information below, we want to make sure that you understand the purposes of this project and the importance of your involvement.

Please read all information carefully and do not hesitate to ask any question you might have to the LET'S CARE researchers who are present.

If you want to participate after having read the information below, you can sign this document to say so.

By signing this document, I agree to participate in the LET'S CARE Network. I confirm:

- That I have read the below information sheet.
- That I understand the information presented there.
- That I had the opportunity to ask questions and that all my questions have been answered.
- That I have received sufficient time to take the decision and that I did not feel pressured to make a choice.
- That I am aware that participation is completely voluntary and that I can change my mind and withdraw my consent to participate at any time. This includes stopping my participation even when I already started. I understand I do not have to provide any justification.

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

INFORMATION SHEET

Here we answer the following questions:

1. Do I have to participate? What happens if I say no, and can I change my mind?
2. What do I do if I have questions?
3. What is the LET'S CARE project?
4. What is the LET'S CARE Network? What is the goal of the Network?
5. What will be my role in the LET'S CARE Network of Stakeholders?
6. Is there a benefit for me in participating?
7. Is there a risk involved for me in participating?
8. WhThe participation of your organization in the Let's Care Network of Stakeholders is free and voluntary. You can say no and reject our invitation. Nothing will happen if you say no.at information will you collect about me?
9. Why do you need that information?
10. What will you do with that information? Who has access to my information?
11. How long will you keep my information?
12. Do I have rights? How can I exercise them?

1. Do I have to participate? What happens if I say no, and can I change my mind?

Also, if you agree to participate, you can change your mind and stop at any time.

Note that you do not have to tell us why you do not want to participate or want to stop (but you can if you want).

2. What do I do if I have questions?

If you have any questions or suggestions, you can tell them to the LET'S CARE project representatives who are present or contact them later at *[Add name and contact details of organisation and the specific person in charge for LET'S CARE]*.

3. What is the LET'S CARE project?

LET'S CARE is a European research project. The main goal of this project is to comprehensively understand and improve the caring dimension of educational inclusion and school success.

The project aims to identify what are the factors that affect student security and how these factors cause underachievement, disengagement, and school dropout, at four (4) different levels: individual, relational, community, and political.

Based on the results of the research, LET'S CARE will create a theoretical and practical framework to foster Safe Learning, Safe Teaching, Safe School, and Safe Education at each of the above-mentioned levels, with the purpose to break the chain of transmission of educational and social exclusion.

4. What is the Network of Stakeholders? What is the goal of the Network?

LET'S CARE Network of Stakeholders is a European active environment of participation constituted by members encompassing representatives of all the relevant stakeholders to contribute to the critical process of feedback loops on the project's activities and results.

It is a real and virtual space in which the principles of the Safe Education approach are promoted and supported through the involvement of scientific community, students, families, teachers, school boards, policymakers, NGOs.

The Network creates a European-wide link between professionals and organizations who share common understanding of the importance of preventing exclusion, underachievement, disengagement and school dropout through the creation of a safe educational environment for all learners.

5. What will be my role in the LET'S CARE Network of Stakeholders?

You can freely choose among different levels of participation to the activities of the Network:

a. Recipients of information: At the most basic level, you can choose to be recipients of information and participants in the LET'S CARE Hub communities. In this role, you will be kept informed about the project's developments, goals, and activities. This role is crucial for those who wish to stay updated and potentially share this information within their own networks, albeit without active involvement in the project's activities.

b. Contributors to dissemination: You can contribute to the dissemination of the project's concepts and principles, centered around fostering a Safe Education environment. This role involves actively spreading awareness and information about the LET'S CARE project within their communities and networks.

c. Active participants in co-creation and PAR: you can also choose to be more actively involved as participants in co-creation and Participatory Action Research (PAR). This involves engaging in activities such as contributing practices, participating in the DELPHI validation process, and being involved in stakeholder interviews. This role is ideal for those who wish to have a hands-on impact on the project's direction and outcomes.

d. Advocates for policy and action: In the most active role, you can serve as advocate, supporting and promoting policy actions that align with the network's goals. This role entails actively pushing for changes, mobilizing resources, and forming alliances to support the cause of Safe Education at various levels.

6. Is there a benefit for me in participating?

The advantages of being part of school in the Let's Care Network of Stakeholders will be:

- Receive specific information on Safe Teaching to improve the academic results and inclusion of all the students.
- Understand the dynamics of successful academic results and reduce the drop-out rates.

- Belong to a network of support and exchange of safe educational practices.
- Get to know new educational strategies and good practices.
- Take advantage of the direct results of the piloting phase.
- Strengthen the collaboration among schools and institutions at the European level.
- Be able to develop, promote and encourage the implementation of quality, sustainable and inclusive educational practices, projects and activities.
- Be involved in dialogue, reflection, cooperation and innovation in the educational field.

7. Is there a risk involved for me in participating?

We think there is no risk involved for you. We tried to create a safe environment for all participants. Also, we value all experiences and opinions. Remember that if you feel that you want to stop your participation, you may always do so.

8. What information will you collect about me?

We will collect the following information:

- Name and address of the organization (in case you are applying as organization);
- Identifying information of the legal representative of the organization (in case you are applying as organization);
- Identifying information of a contact persons;
- Contact information of a contact person.

9. Why do you need that information?

The personal and/or organization information will be collected to:

- include them in the database of all the European stakeholders that are involved in the project and are willing to be informed and support the development and implementation of the “Safe Education”;
- inform the contact person about the project’s opportunities;
- invite the contact person to participate to the sub-communities of interest;
- facilitate the contacts among the participating organization;
- encourage exchanges, dissemination of good practices and all activities aimed at improving inclusive and Safe education.

10. What will you do with that information? Who has access to my information?

The information about the legal representative of the school will be used only for administrative reasons for the signature of the agreement.

The name and the contact information of the contact person will be internally used to inform the organization about the project's proceedings and results.

The LET'S CARE partners will have access to the collected data. The LET'S CARE partners are all in the European Union. We do not plan to share any of your data outside the European Economic Area.

11. How long will you keep my information?

We will keep the information until five (5) years after the end of the project. The project ends in September 2025, so we will keep your information until September 2030. We will keep it for so long because we have a contractual obligation to do so.

For as long as we use your information, we will respect the laws that tell us what we can and cannot do with your information.

12. Do I have rights? How can I exercise them?

Yes, of course. In the first place, you can always decide to stop your participation.

In addition, you have other rights, such as:

- You can ask us for more information.
- You can ask us to know what information we have on you.
- You can ask us to delete information.
- You can ask us to make correct the information.
- You can ask us to see the data we have collected and obtain a copy.

However, since we are not asking for your name, we will most likely not be able to identify which testimony, and/or inputs provided during the discussion are yours. For this reason, it will be difficult to make corrections or to delete information afterwards.

If you have questions about this, you can contact us in this way: *[Add name and contact details of organisation and the specific person in charge for LET'S CARE]*.

If you contact us and you are not happy, you can submit a complaint to the competent national data protection authority, in this case, the *[Add information about the National Data Protection Authorities]* Because of language barriers, you could ask your local data protection authority (you can find your local data protection authority contact details following this link: https://edpb.europa.eu/about-edpb/about-edpb/members_en#member-at) for help. Nevertheless, we will always try to avoid that you need to do this, by answering your questions and helping you out whenever we can.

Annex 2 – Initial map of the stakeholders that can be potentially involved in the LET’S CARE Network

1. Bulgaria

Name of the stakeholder	of the Stakeholder target group	type - Geographical level of impact	Short description of the stakeholder and of its activities	Website	Potential contribution to the project
National Association of Resource Teachers	Teachers Policy makers	National International	The Association implements National and international projects; promote professional competency; Advocate for appropriate research-based education and therapy for all children, youth and families	https://www.narubg.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results
Association for Shared Learning	Students Parents	National International	It is a center for Inclusive Education Expertise in the field of social-emotional learning, inclusive education, child protection, child participation,	https://www.ela-bg.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results Help to promote the project and enlarge the targeted Schools

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			civic and environmental education, school mediation.		
Regional Center for Supporting the Process of Inclusive Education	Government structures	Regional National	There are 17 Regional Specialized service unit of the Ministry of Education and Science for the implementation of the state policy for inclusive education in the Sofia city district	https://rcsf.bg	Dissemination of the aims and results Help to promote the project and enlarge the targeted Schools Advocacy
Marie Curie Association	NGO	Regional	MCA is a non-profit Organisation in Plovdiv, Bulgaria. Promote the universal design of learning as type of learning/training approach will support the achievement of the ultimate goal of increasing social cohesion and integration of children with learning difficulties in the education	https://www.mariecurie.bg	Dissemination of the aims and results Advocacy
Association "Parents"	Parents	National	The association is involved in	https://roditeli.org	Support the

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	Education scientific community		the development, implementation and dissemination of regional and national policies. It also provide assistance for the development of children's healthcare		development documents/ research Implement round tables Dissemination of the aims and results
Association "Pelago"	Students Parents	Regional	The NGO works for family in child development: training parents and professionals working with children	https://pelagobg.eu	Support the implementation of Teachers Training Support the development documents/ research
Foundation "Association Animus"	Students Families Education scientific community General public	National	Center for recovery, counselling, psychotherapy and psychoanalysis. Working with difficult children and children with specific problems.	https://animusassociation.org	Dissemination of the aims and results
OU "Stefan Peshev" Primary and Middle	School	Local	Pre-primary, primary, middle school	http://ou2-sevlievo.com	Dissemination of the aims and results

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School - Sevlievo					Participation to the Community of Schools
OU Vasil Levski -Midle school Schumata	School	Local	Primary school for bilingual children from minority groups	https://www.ou-schumata.com	Dissemination of the aims and results Participation to the Community of Schools
OU Kiril i Metodii Primary School - Malorad	School	Local	Primary school with a high presence of children from minority groups	https://ou-kirilimetodii.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results Participation to the Community of Schools
Department of Education in Sevlievo Municipality	Policy maker and authority	Local Regional	The department implements municipal policies for the development of children's interests, abilities and competences. It has special attention for children at risk and with disabilities	https://www.sevlievo.bg	Dissemination of the aims and results
Professional forum for education	NGOs	National International	The association informs, participates in committees on	https://obrazovatenforum.wixsite.com/pf	Dissemination of the aims and results

			innovations and quality of education in the Ministry of Education	orumedu	Advocacy
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2. Italy

Name of the stakeholder	Stakeholder target group	Stakeholder type	Geographical level of impact	Short description of the stakeholder and of its activities	Website	Potential contribution to the project
University of Verona - Department of Human Sciences	Education Community	Scientific	National	The department implements degree programmes and research in several areas: philosophy, pedagogy, psychology, political philosophy, sociology and anthropology.	https://www.dsu.univr.it	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results, Transfer of results

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<p>University of Verona - Department of Cultures and civilizations</p>	<p>Education Scientific Community</p>	<p>National</p>	<p>The department implements degree courses and research in various areas: historical, literary and art historical disciplines, archaeology, geography, anthropology, philology, linguistics and performing arts</p>	<p>https://www.dcuci.univr.it</p>	<p>Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results, Transfer of results</p>
<p>University of Padua - Department of Philosophy, Sociology, Pedagogy and Applied Psychology</p>	<p>Education Scientific Community</p>	<p>National</p>	<p>The department coordinates didactics and research in a broad area of the humanities and social sciences. The Department is particularly active in the dissemination of scientific knowledge and in</p>	<p>https://www.fisppa.unipd.it</p>	<p>Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results</p>

			territorial interventions in cooperation with public and private entities.		
Institute for the Deaf in Turin	Students Families Teachers NGOs General Public	Regional	The Institute works for the education and social inclusion of deaf people	https://istitutosorditorino.org	Policy recommendations Transfer of results Advocacy
Association Giuseppe Pacini	Students NGOs	Local Regional	The association promotes and develops software for blind students that enables them to study mathematics, science and music		Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy

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Fondazione Opera Edimar	Families NGO	Local Regional	Centre for supporting people with learning difficulties and their families	https://www.operaedimar.com	Dissemination of the aims and results Advocacy
C.R.E.A. INSIEME Srl - centre for educational networks and assistance	Students Families Teachers NGOs	Local	Centre of educational support to students with educational difficulties and for teachers training.	https://www.creainsieme.com	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results
Educa Piu'	Students Families NGOs	Local Regional	Association for the educational support to students with educational difficulties.		Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results
Cooperativa La Fucina	Students	Local	Learning Centre and Science Dissemination	http://www.lafucinad	Dissemination of the

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delle Scienze	Education Community NGOs	Scientific	Regional		ellescienze.it	aims and results Transfer of results
Fondazione La Città Invisibile	Students NGOs		Local Regional	Association that promotes inclusion and involvement in orchestral music training activities of children from social at risks contexts (i.e. criminality)	https://fondazioneici.wixsite.com/lacittainvisibile	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results
Assocition Piccoli Mondi	NGOs		International	Support for children in real or educational need, including orphans and disabled children from any country in the world	https://piccolimondi.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy

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Associazione PiùPer	NGOs	International	Volunteer association for the teachers training and the promotion of innovative pedagogy.	https://piuper.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results
Associazione Italiana Farfalle	Families NGOs	National	Association that supports and promotes the talent, creativity and giftedness of children and young people aged 3 to 19, their parents and teachers	https://www.associazi onefarfalle.it	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results
AGET- Associazione Genitori Education to Talent	Families NGOs	National	Parent's association that promotes knowledge on the topic of high cognitive potential, organises events for gifted children and young people in order to enhance and	http://www.agetitalia. it	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy

			develop their abilities		
Associazione Culturale Lo Sbuffo – Accademia digitale	Students NGOs General public	National	Promotes digital literacy, Interculturalism, Countering fake news, Adapting the education system to the needs of civil society and the market, In-company training, Increasing programmes and paths that encourage young people to participate in the political life of the country	https://losbuffo.com	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results
Cooperativa Cultura e Valori	Students Families Teachers	Local	The cooperative manages different schools (from kindergartens to VET schools) and professional training courses for educators	http://www.culturaev valori.it	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results

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Associazione onlus	AIAS	Students Families Teachers NGOs General Public	Local Regional	It supports disabled adults in managing daily life, organises recreational and leisure activities with outings and holiday stays for children, young people and young adults of all ages.	https://www.aiasbo.it	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy
Fondazione Più di un Sogno		Students Families NGOs	Local Regional	The foundation supports people with Down syndrome and intellectual disabilities to help them achieve a better quality of life	https://piudiunsogno.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy
Network of schools of Mountain (Lessinia area)		Students Teachers	Local	Network of 6 Comprehensive institutes located in the mountain area of Lessinia		Dissemination of the aims and results

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	Schools					Transfer of results Help to promote the project and enlarge the targeted Schools
Ufficio Regionale degli Studi del Veneto	Policy Makers	Regional	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the regional level	https://istruzioneevento.gov.it		Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Verona	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the provincial level	https://win.istruzione.verona.it/uspvr		Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Vicenza	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the	https://vicenza.istruziooneveneto.gov.it		Public Administration knowledge and resources

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				provincial level		Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Padova	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the provincial level	https://padova.istruzi oneveneto.gov.it	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations	
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Venezia	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the provincial level	https://venezia.istruzi oneveneto.gov.it	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations	
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Rovigo	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the provincial level	https://www.istruzione erovigo.it	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results	

					Policy recommendations
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Treviso	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the provincial level	https://treviso.istruzioneveneto.gov.it	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Belluno	Policy Makers	Local	Ministerial office responsible for the implementation of public education policies at the provincial level	https://belluno.istruzioneveneto.gov.it	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations

3. Lithuania

Name	of the Stakeholder type	- Geographical	Short description	of the Website	Potential contribution
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stakeholder	target group	level of impact	stakeholder and of its activities	to the project
Panevezys "Šaltinio" progymnazium	Students Families Teachers Schools	Regional	General education school https://saltinioprojimnazija.lt	Dissemination of the aims and results Participation to the Community of Schools
Panevezys district r. Raguvos gymnazium	Students Families Teachers Schools	Regional	General education school https://raguvosgimnazija.lt	Dissemination of the aims and results Participation to the Community of Schools
Panevezys district Krekenavos "Sigute" kindergarten	Students Families Teachers Schools	Regional	General education pre-school https://krekenavossigute.lt	Dissemination of the aims and results Participation to the Community of Schools
Panevezys district Naujamiestis school	Students Families Teachers Schools	Regional	General education school https://nvmokykla.lt	Dissemination of the aims and results Participation to the Community of Schools

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Administration of Panevėžys district municipality	Public Administration	National	Responsible for the preparation of public education policy at the regional level	www.panrs.lt	Help to promote the project and enlarge the targeted Schools Dissemination, Transfer of results, policy recommendation
Association of Lithuanian Education Center Managers	NGO	National	Responsible for the qualification of Lithuanian teachers		Help to promote the project and enlarge the targeted Schools Dissemination, Transfer of results, policy recommendation

4. Poland

Name of the stakeholder	Stakeholder target group	type - Geographical level of impact	Short description of the stakeholder and of its activities	Website	Potential contribution to the project
Zespół Szkół i Placówek Specjalnych	Students Education Community Teachers Schools	Scientific Local	School for children with difficulties	www.kr.edu.pl	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Participation to the Community of Schools Advocacy
Zespół Szkół Specjalnych	Students Education Community Teachers Schools	Scientific Local	School for children and youngsters with disabilities	http://www.zss4krakow.pl	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Participation to the Community of Schools Advocacy
Szkoła Podstawowa w Pstroszycach	Students Families	Local	Mainstream education - primary school in a rural area	http://sppstroszyce.pl	Research, dissemination, Transfer

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Pierwszych	Teachers School				of results
I Lo w Limanowej	Students Families Teachers School	Local	Mainstream education - high school		Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Participation to the Community of Schools
ZSE we Wrocławiu	Students Families Teachers School	Local	Mainstream education - high school	https://www.drukarska.net	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Participation to the Community of Schools
I LO w Rabce Zdroju	Students Families Teachers School	Local	Mainstream education - high school	https://romer.nowotaraki.edu.pl	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Participation to the Community of Schools
UMiG Tymbark	Policy makers	Local	Municipal office	https://www.tymbark.pl	Help to promote the

				pl	<p>project and enlarge the targeted Schools</p> <p>Dissemination of the aims and results</p> <p>Policy Recommendations</p>
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5. Portugal

Name of the stakeholder	Stakeholder type - Geographical level of impact	target group	Short description of the stakeholder and of its activities	Website	Potential contribution to the project
Cruz Vermelha Portuguesa [Portuguese Red Cross]	NGO	National	To advocate for peace, uphold the reverence for the dignity of every human being, mitigate the consequences of warfare, and foster the preservation of life and well-being.	https://www.cruzvermelha.pt	<p>Dissemination of results</p> <p>Advocacy</p> <p>Policy recommendations</p>
APEI Associação de	Education community	National	Promote continuous	https://apei.pt	Research,

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Profissionais de Educação de Infância			information and training for members; encourage innovation in educational practices and research in the field of early childhood education; undertake joint actions with other similar associations; advocate for the interests of members.		dissemination, Transfer of results Policy recommendations
EDULOG - Fundação Belmiro de Azevedo	Education scientific Community NGO	National	EDULOG is an institution associated with the field of Education, dedicated to research, analysis, and discussion of the Portuguese education system.	https://www.edulog.pt	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results Policy recommendations
Fundação José Neves	NGO	National	Intervening in Portugal's growth through education as a promoter of human potential development. Promoting access	https://www.joseneves.org	Research, dissemination, Advocacy

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			to learning, enhancing future skills, envisioning education of the future, and fostering personal development.		
Ordem dos Psicólogos Portugueses	Education scientific community Policy maker and authority	National	The Ordem dos Psicólogos Portugueses is the professional public association representing psychologists in Portugal. Research, training, Organisation of the practice and access to the psychology profession, development of ethical and deontological standards, promotion of the role of psychologists in society, fostering a practice of excellence that protects all clients and recipients of psychological services.	https://www.ordemdospicologos.pt	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Support the development documents/ research Policy Recommendations
Cáritas Portuguesa	NGO Citizens, media outlet	National	Cáritas in Portugal has a mission to promote Integral Human	https://caritas.pt	Dissemination of the aims and results

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	and general public	International	Development and advocate for the Common Good, working towards the transformation of society.		Advocacy Policy recommendations
ACM - Alto Comissariado para as Migrações	Policy maker and authority	National International	It is a public institute that participates in the implementation of public policies regarding migrations. It takes a creative approach to addressing the growing needs of different migrant profiles and their integration. It develops programs for the social inclusion of descendants of immigrants, a relevant topic within the scope of the project.	https://www.acm.gov.pt/pt/acm	Dissemination of the aims and results Advocacy Support the development documents/ research Policy Recommendations
IAVE - Instituto de Avaliação Educativa	Education Scientific Community NGO	National	It is a public institute under the supervision of the Portuguese Ministry of Education, with the main function of exam and assessment, training and	https://iave.pt	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Policy

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			supervision (designing and organizing teacher training programs in the specific domain of learning assessment), report production.		recommendations
UMAR - União de Mulheres Alternativa e Resposta	NGO Citizens, media outlet and general public	National	It is an association that aims to empower socially committed feminism, dedicated to raising feminist awareness in Portuguese society. It focuses on issues related to discrimination, inequalities, and social inclusion, which are central themes to the project.	http://www.umarfeminismos.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Advocacy
EPIS - Associação Empresários pela Inclusão	NGO Citizens, media outlet and general public	National	A group of over 100 Portuguese entrepreneurs and managers dedicated to identification and systematization of best management practices in Portuguese schools; promotion of effort, merit, and justice for	https://www.epis.pt	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results

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			lifelong personal fulfillment.		
EDUPA - Associação para o Desenvolvimento Pessoal	Education scientific community	National	Association that promotes mindfulness and educational coaching in a school setting. It promotes training in Clinical and Educational Psychology.	https://edupa.pt	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results
IDR - Centro de Inclusão Social da Madeira	Students Families NGO Citizens, media outlet and general public	National	Psychosocial rehabilitation and therapy centre for the population with disabilities. It promotes socially useful occupational activities.	https://www.idr.madeira.gov.pt	Research, dissemination, Advocacy
IIE – Instituto de Inovação Educacional - porsinal	Education scientific community	National	It aims to promote and support educational innovation through scientific, technical, and financial means. It seeks to establish a connection between schools, administration, research, and policy-making, contributing to educational decision-making processes.	https://www.porsinal.pt/index.php?ps=directorio&cat=27&iddir=387	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results

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<p>Olhares Inclusivos - Portugal Inovação Social</p>	<p>Families NGO Citizens, media outlet and general public</p>	<p>National</p>	<p>A program of training and support for parents, families, informal caregivers, professionals, and other practitioners, a plan for disseminating good practices and raising awareness for inclusion and equality, and a program for developing emotional, personal, and social skills, with activities related to creativity, arts, environment, and citizenship.</p>	<p>https://inovacaosocial.portugal2020.pt/project/olhares-inclusivos/?doing_wp_cron=1688941591.3894839286804199218750</p>	<p>Research, dissemination, Transfer of results</p>
<p>Faculdade de Psicologia Universidade de Lisboa</p>	<p>Education scientific community</p>	<p>National International</p>	<p>Academic institution that can bring technical and scientific knowledge around the topics covered in the project</p>	<p>https://www.psicologia.ulisboa.pt/</p>	<p>Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results Policy recommendations</p>

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Escola de Psicologia da Universidade do Minho	Education scientific community	National International	Academic institution	https://www.psi.uminho.pt	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results Policy recommendations
ISPA	Education scientific community	National International	Academic institution on psychology and behavioural sciences	www.ispa.pt	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results Policy recommendations
Prochild COLAB	Students Families Education scientific community	National International	Collaborative laboratory on children and poverty. It develops research and provides training and other services.	https://prochildcolab.pt	Research, dissemination, Advocacy

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Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian	Education scientific community NGO	National International	It brings out research, analysis, and discussion of the Portuguese education system; strategic planning of education.	https://gulbenkian.pt	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results, policy recommendation
Projeto Social Aventura	NGO	National International	It is a project about research and intervention on Education	https://aventurasocial.com	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results,
CIIL - Centro de Investigação e Intervenção na Leitura (Instituto Politécnico do Porto, Câmara Municipal do Porto, Ministério da Educação de Portugal)	Education scientific community	National	It develops research and intervention on reading	https://www.ipp.pt/investigacao/centros-de-investigacao/educacao/ciil	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results
Brave Generation	NGO	National	It aims to promote and support	https://bravegenerati	Dissemination,

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Academy	Citizens, media outlet and general public		educational innovation through technical, and financial means.	onacademy.com	Transfer of results
SAME - Serviço de Apoio à Melhoria da Educação	Education scientific community	National	Service provided by the Faculty of Education and Psychology of Universidade Católica Portuguesa, aimed to support schools and other educational institutions.	https://www.porto.ucp.pt/pt/same	Support the development documents/ research Dissemination of the aims and results
Teach for Portugal	Teachers	National	It integrates international network "Teach for All"; aims to reduce educational inequality	https://teachforportugal.org/	Research, dissemination, Advocacy Policy recommendations
IPDJ - Instituto Português do Desporto e Juventude	NGO Citizens, media outlet and general public	National	Public institute focused on the development of national policy on sports and youth	www.ipdj.pt	Research, dissemination, Transfer of results Policy

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					recommendations
Academia de Líderes Ubuntu - Escolas Ubuntu	Students Teachers	National and International	Part of the Ubuntu Leadership Academy; aims to promote leadership skills in schools. It offers training program to teachers and students, based on leadership skills.	https://academialideresubuntu.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Advocacy
Programa Escolhas	Public funding	National	Public institution focused on funding community-based projects for vulnerable youth. Most projects offer out-of-school educational support to vulnerable children and adolescents	http://www.programaescolhas.pt /	Dissemination of the aims and results Advocacy

6. Spain

Name of the stakeholder	the Stakeholder target group	type - Geographical level of impact	Short description of the stakeholder and of its activities	Website	Potential contribution to the project
Fundación Empieza por Educar	Teachers	National International	Each year they roll out a professional development programme aimed at those who aspire to bring about educational and social change for the benefit of equal opportunities for all children.	https://empiezaporeducar.org	Training for future teachers
Facultad Educación- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Education scientific community	Local National	University faculty for future Teachers	https://www.uam.es	Support the development documents/ research Teacher training
Fundación Bofiil	NGOs, advocacy organizations	Local National	A research and proposals laboratory focused on the field of education that works to promote research, debates and initiatives to generate educational opportunities and	https://fundaciobofiil.cat	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results

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			combat social inequalities.		
OCDE	Policy maker and authority	International	Innovative Teaching for Effective Learning project	https://www.oecd.org/education/cei/innovative-teaching-for-effective-learning.htm	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results
Iniciativa Educaçao	Education scientific community	National International	It helps ensure young people achieve educational success, by supporting exemplary projects that have the potential to be replicated in both the educational system and in society at large	https://www.iniciativaeducacao.org	Support the development documents/ research Teacher training
EduCaixa	NGOs, advocacy organizations	National	The Organisation provides school management teams, teachers and students with multiple resources to make learning richer, more meaningful and more holistic.	https://educaixa.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy
Fundación SM	NGOs, advocacy organizations	National	It is a non-profit educational institution that works to	https://www.fundacion-sm.org	Dissemination of the aims and results

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		international	ensure that, through education and culture, no child is left behind. They focus all their initiatives on improving educational equity and quality.		Transfer of results Advocacy
Ies Francisco De Quevedo	School	Local	Secondary school and vocational education with a high level of diversity	https://www.educa2.madrid.org/web/centro.ies.quevedo.madrid	Participation to the Community of Schools
Fundación Tomillo	NGOs, advocacy organizations	Local	A ONG that accompanies young people in vulnerable situations to boost their growth and employability through an innovative, lively and open socio-educational model.	https://tomillo.org/	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy
Fundación Secretariado Gitano	NGOs, advocacy organizations	Local National	The FSG develops all kinds of actions that contribute to achieving full citizenship of Roma people, to improve their	https://www.gitanos.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Transfer of results Advocacy

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			living conditions, to promote equal treatment and to avoid all forms of discrimination, as well as to promote the recognition of the cultural identity of the roma community		
Consejería de Educacion y Deporte de Andalucía	Public Administration	Regional Andalucía	- Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	http://www.juntadeandalucia.es	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Departamento de Educación, Cultura y Deporte	Public Administration	Regional-Aragón	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.educara.gon.org	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations

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Consejería de Educación de Asturias	Public Administration	Regional- Asturias	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.educastur.es	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación y Universidad de Islas Baleares	Public Administration	Regional - Islas Baleares	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.caib.es/sites/educacio/	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación, Universidades, Cultura y Deportes	Public Administration	Regional- Canarias	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/educacion/web/	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de	Public Administration	Regional-	Administration responsible for	https://www.educant	Public Administration

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Educación , Formación Porfesional y Turismo		Cantabria	the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	abria.es/	knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación de Castilla - Mancha	Public Administration	Regional- Castilla - La Mancha	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	http://www.educa.jccm.es/	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Departamento de Educación de Cataluña	Public Administration	Regional- Cataluña	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	http://ensenyament.gencat.cat/	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación y Empleo	Public Administration	Regional - Extremadura	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public	https://educarex.es/	Public Administration knowledge and

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de Extremadura			education policies at the regional level		resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación de Galicia	Public Administration	Regional-Galicia	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.edu.xunta.gal	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación y Juventud de Madrid	Public Administration	Regional-Madrid	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/educacion	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación y Cultura de Murcia	Public Administration	Regional-Murcia	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the	https://www.educarm.es	Public Administration knowledge and resources

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			regional level		Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Departamento de Educación de Navarra	Public Administration	Regional- Navarra	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.educacion.navarra.es	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Consejería de Educación, Cultura, Deporte y Juventud	Public Administration	Regional- La Rioja	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	http://www.larioja.org/educacion	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Departamento de Educación del País Vasco	Public Administration	Regional- País Vasco	Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	https://www.euskadi.eus/educacion	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results

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					Policy recommendations
Conselleria de Educación, Cultura y Deporte de Valencia	Public Administration	Regional Valencia	- Administration responsible for the elaboration of public education policies at the regional level	http://www.ceice.gva.es	Public Administration knowledge and resources Transfer of results Policy recommendations
Federación Española de Religiosos de Enseñanza	NGOs and advocacy organizations	National	Organisation approved by the Holy See in 1957 that groups together the Orders, Congregations and religious Institutes with educational centers in Spain.	https://www.ecmadri.org	Dissemination of the aims and results Help to promote the project and enlarge the targeted Schools
Confederación Española de Asociaciones de Padres y Madres de Alumnado (CEAPA)	Families	National	A social, non-denominational, progressive and independent Organisation that works for a quality public school, to achieve school success for all students, to democratize	https://www.ceapa.es	Advocacy

			education and to improve the conditions of children.	
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7. European & Global stakeholders

Name of the stakeholder	Stakeholder type - target group	Geographical level of impact	Short description of the stakeholder and of its activities	Website	Potential contribution to the project
European School Heads Association	Policy maker and authority	European	Representative organisation of school leaders in Europe	https://esha.org	Dissemination of the aims and results
OBESSU	Students	European	Representative organisation of secondary school students in Europe	https://obessu.org	Dissemination of the aims and results
ATEE	Teachers Education scientific community	European	Representative organisation of teacher training universities	https://atee.education	Dissemination of the aims and results
AEDE	Teachers	European	European-minded teachers' organisation	https://www.aede.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results
Euroclio	Teachers	European	Organisation of history and	https://euroclio.eu	Dissemination of the

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			civics teachers		aims and results
SIRIUS	Education scientific community Teachers Policy Makers	European	Organisation supporting the education of migrants	https://www.sirius-migrationeducation.org	Dissemination of the aims and results
Lifelong Learning Platform	NGOs	European	Education NGOs with EU scope	https://lllplatform.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results
EFIL	NGOs	European	Intercultural learning projects and advocacy	https://efil.afs.org	Dissemination of the aims and results
School Education Platform	EU institution	European	EU platform for education	https://school-education.ec.europa.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results
European Federation of Psychologists Associations	NGOs	European	Organisation of psychologists	https://ehps.net	Dissemination of the aims and results
European Association of Education Researchers	Education scientific community	European	Organisation of education researchers	https://eera-ecer.de	Dissemination of the aims and results

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European Distance and E-Learning Network	Teachers	European	Platform for organisations interested in or implementing digital learning	https://eden-europe.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results
EUCEN	Education scientific community	European	Multidisciplinary Association in University Lifelong Learning	https://eucen.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results
European Commission DG EAC	European institution	European	Directorate General for education	https://commission.europa.eu/topics/education-and-training_en	Dissemination of the aims and results
European Commission DG EMPL	European institution	European	Directorate General responsible for vocational training	https://ec.europa.eu/social/home.jsp	Dissemination of the aims and results
European Parliament CULT Committee	European institution	European	Parliamentary committee covering education	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/en/cult	Dissemination of the aims and results
European Parliament Intergroup on Child Rights	European institution	European	Parliamentary group of interested MEPs		Dissemination of the aims and results
European Parliamentary Research Service	European institution	European	offering background services for the EP	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/at-your-service/en/stay-	Dissemination of the aims and results

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				informed/research-and-analysis	
Joint Research Centre	European institution	European	Organisation offering background services for policy making	https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/joint-research-centre_en	Dissemination of the aims and results
Innocenti Research Centre	Global institution	International	Organisation providing services for policy making with a child rights focus	https://www.unicef-irc.org	Dissemination of the aims and results
EcoSoc	NGOs	International	Social and educational NGOs at the UN	https://www.un.org/ecosoc	Dissemination of the aims and results
INGO conference	NGOs	European	Social and educational NGOs at the Council of Europe	https://coe.int/en/web/ingo	Dissemination of the aims and results
Council of Europe Better Education for Better Democracies	European institution	European	Education policy body at the Council of Europe	https://www.coe.int	Dissemination of the aims and results

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Fundamental Rights Agency	European institution	European	Rights-oriented services for policy making	https://fra.europa.eu	Dissemination of the aims and results
OECD	European institution	European International	Organisation supporting education policy making	https://www.oecd.org	Dissemination of the aims and results

Annex 3 – Initial members informally involved in the LET’S CARE Network

Partner	Country	Name of the Stakeholder	Type of stakeholder	Geographical level of impact	Mean used for providing information
PROMA	Spain	Fundación SM	NGOs, organizations advocacy	National-International	Personal meeting
PROMA	Spain	Fundación Empieza por Educar	Teacher’s community	National-International	Personal meeting
PROMA	Spain	Facultad Educación - Universidad Autónoma de Madrid	Education community scientific	Local-National	Personal meeting
PROMA	Spain	Fundación Bofill	NGOs, organizations advocacy	Local-National	Personal meeting
PROMA	Spain	Educaixa	NGOs, organizations advocacy	National	Personal meeting
PROMA	Spain	Ies Francisco De Quevedo	School	Local	Personal meeting
PROMA	Spain	Fundación Tomillo	NGOs, organizations advocacy	Local	Personal meeting

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			organizations		
PROMA	Spain	Fundación Secretariado Gitano	NGOs, organizations	advocacy	Local-National Personal meeting
KITE	Bulgaria	Krassimira Jordanova	Policy Makers		Regional Newsletters
KITE	Bulgaria	Association Professional Forum for Education NGO-APFE Contact person: Svetlana Nancheva	NGO		National WEB site, Newsletters
PRSC	Lithuania	Panevezys "Šaltinio" progymnazium	Policy Makers		Local e-mail, newsletter
PRSC	Lithuania	Panevezys district r. Raguvos gymnazium	Policy Makers		Local Newsletter
PRSC	Lithuania	Association "Tell me more"	NGO		National Newsletter
POLO	Italy	University of Padua - Department of Philosophy,	Education Community	Scientific	National Direct contacts

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		Sociology, Pedagogy and Applied Psychology			
POLO	Italy	Associazione Giuseppe Pacini	Students NGOs	Local Regional	Direct contact – mailing list
POLO	Italy	Cooperativa Culturale e Valori	Students Families Teachers	Local	Direct contact
POLO	Italy	Fondazione Più di un Sogno	Students Families NGOs	Local Regional	Direct contact – mailing list
POLO	Italy	Ufficio Regionale degli Studi del Veneto	Policy Makers	Regional	Direct contact
POLO	Italy	Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Verona	Policy Makers	Local	Direct contact
POLO	Italy	Ufficio Provinciale degli Studi di Vicenza	Policy Makers	Local	Direct contact

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POLO	Italy	Provincial network of school with helpdesk for autism and neurodivergency (province of Verona)	NGO	Provincial	Direct contacts
POLO	Italy	Regional network of the 0-6 years old education	Teacher's community	Regional	Direct contacts
UCP	Portugal	Escola Básica Integrada de Rabo de Peixe	School	Local	Direct contacts
UCP	Portugal	Colégio Nossa Senhora do Rosário	School	Local	Direct contacts
UCP	Portugal	General Directorate of Education of the Portuguese Ministry of Education	Policy Makers	National	Direct contacts
UCP	Portugal	Portuguese parliament's commission on Education	Policy Makers	National	Direct contacts